

Reasons for Afghan Immigrants to Come to Turkey and the Problems They Experience

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Abstract

When we look at the countries with the largest immigrant population in the world, it is seen that factors such as internal conflict, war, and a weak economy are one of the main reasons for migration mobility. Due to the ongoing conflicts in Afghanistan for years, it has maintained its position as the country that produces the most immigrants in the world. In this study, we tried to understand the socio-economic characteristics of Afghan immigrants living in Istanbul, Konya, Uşak, and Sakarya, based on their experiences in the migration process and examining the reasons for their migration. The "survey" method was chosen as the data collection method. Questionnaires were prepared appropriately and applied in the form of face-to-face interviews. The data obtained through the questionnaire were evaluated by preparing tables consisting of frequency and percentage distributions. We evaluated our findings and results in terms of the socio-economy of the immigrants and then the reasons for their arrival in Turkey. Prolonged conflicts and drought and famine caused by climate change, which created an uncertain economic and political situation in Afghanistan, forced about 7 million Afghans to leave their homeland and migrate to other countries to find a better life. To prevent the Afghan migration crisis that has been going on for years, first of all, political and economic stability must be ensured. To ensure economic and political stability in Afghanistan, it is necessary to establish an inclusive and unifying government that includes all ethnic groups. In terms of economy, since the country's economy is predominantly based on agriculture, agricultural policies and programs should be developed and farmers should be supported.

Keywords: Afghanistan, migration, afghan immigrants, immigration to Turkey

1. INTRODUCTION

Afghanistan continues to be the country that receives the most immigrants in the world for many years due to political instability, worsening security, and economic problems. According to the data of the United Nations, Afghanistan is currently the second country seeking refugees in the world, after Syria. Almost 50 years of unending war and instability in Afghanistan have negatively affected the living conditions of people and forced them to migrate internally and externally. More than 6 million Afghans had to migrate to neighboring countries such as Iran, Pakistan, and Uzbekistan, especially due to the civil wars and their consequences. After Pakistan and Iran, which hosted the most Afghan immigrants in the 2010s, Turkey also entered the field due to its neighbor with Europe. With the acceleration of globalization in the 21st century, international migration has increased significantly. One of the most important features of the growing migration movement is emigration. People living in unstable, underdeveloped, or developing regions of the world migrate to developed countries for better living and working conditions. Factors such as conflict, famine caused by climate change, and political and economic factors are among the most important reasons that lead people to migrate from one place to another (Dashti, 2021). Afghanistan has been the focus of great powers throughout history due to its location. Due to foreign interventions and mono-ethnic policies and long-standing tyranny in the country, many had to migrate, causing immigration to become a part of the country's historical identity. Especially in the last 50 years, due to the devastating results of internal conflicts, authoritarian policies of the rulers, and foreign interventions,

Afghanistan is the country with the highest number of immigrants after Syria. Almost half of Afghanistan's population of 32.9 million (2021) has experienced migration in their lifetime (Dashti, 2021). The fall of the Kabul government on August 15, 2021, and the Taliban came to power for the second time in the country, causing a political and economic crisis. With the economic situation in the country deteriorating, many Afghans are left with no choice but to leave the country. According to reports, with the increase in poverty in the country, many people leave Afghanistan every day. The largest and most massive migration in Afghanistan's history began with the Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan. During the Soviet occupation between 1979-1989 more than 5 million Afghans had to migrate to Iran, Pakistan, Turkey, and other countries. Such a large number amounted to one-fifth of the country's population then. In addition, two million internally displaced people had to move within the country. The second largest mass migration occurred due to the conflict between the groups that could not share power after the Soviet Union's withdrawal from Afghanistan in 1989 and the turmoil created by the civil war (Dashti, 2022). Another mass exodus was triggered in Afghanistan following the complete withdrawal of US and NATO forces from Afghanistan on July 22, 2021, and the Taliban takeover of Afghanistan on August 15, 2021. The fall of the Kabul government and the cessation of foreign aid have deepened the economic crisis in Afghanistan and increased poverty. The above-mentioned reasons have forced Afghan people struggling with hunger to migrate to different countries in order to survive for themselves and their family members. This research is aimed to indicate the reasons for the arrival of Afghan

immigrants to Turkey and the problems they face. It also gives information about the socio-economic characteristics of Afghan immigrants in Turkey and their integration in Turkey.

1.1. Geographical Position of Afghanistan and its Importance in the Region

The importance of Afghanistan comes from its geographical location. In fact, Afghanistan has been the intersection of Central Asia, West and South Asia, the border of continental and oceanic powers, and the home of stronger opposition forces in the region (Tanin, 2005). The geographical location of Afghanistan has given it the status of a bridge between Central Asian and South Asian countries, as shown in Figure 1. In the north of Afghanistan, there are countries such as Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan,

Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan, which are rich in Central Asia's energy resources consisting of gas, electricity, oil, and other raw materials. In the south and east of Afghanistan, there are two countries, Pakistan and India, which are in great need of energy and raw materials. This location has given Afghanistan special geopolitical, geo-economics, and geostrategic importance. Afghanistan borders Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan to the north. Iran is located in western Afghanistan; it is located in the south and east of Pakistan, and in the northeastern part is China. Afghanistan has a total border of 5514 kilometers with its neighbors. This country has a common border of 2384 km with its northern neighbors, about 75 km with China's Xinjiang states, 945 km with Iran, and about 2240 km with Pakistan and Jammu-Kashmir (Rahimi, 2012).

Figure 1. Map of Afghanistan Source: afghanistan-political-map.jpg (1200×986) (geology.com) (30. 06. 2022)

Geographically, Afghanistan, located in the center of Asia, has the status of four roads between the vast regions of this continent (Ghubar, 2009). Afghanistan is one of the four regions of the world that

are densely populated and rich in mineral resources (Central, South Asia, Central, and North Asia, Middle East, and the Far East). While Afghanistan includes small parts of each of these regions and has

cultural, racial, and commercial interests in common with them, it is not specifically related to any of them. However, due to the fact that Afghanistan is within the borders of each of these huge regions, it cannot be separated from any of them. This country is located as a connecting bridge between them (Bina, 2008). Afghanistan has had special importance in the region in terms of geopolitical and geostrategic since ancient times, and many historical events have taken place in this country. Since it was the gateway to India from ancient times to 1800 AD, it was constantly attacked from the north and west. Because it was known as the most convenient way to reach the land of India. Many rulers attacked Afghanistan to reach India in this way, the last empire that wanted to attack India in this way and drive the British out of India was the French Napoleon Bonaparte, whose plan was foiled by the then king of Afghanistan, Shah Zaman (Ghiyasi, 2004). Another capacity and opportunity created by the geography of Afghanistan for this country are water resources. The location of the source of many rivers flowing into neighboring countries in Afghanistan is an opportunity that clearly and significantly increases Afghanistan's bargaining power in regional relations. Afghanistan can use this resource to turn the economic wheel of the country, as well as leverage this resource to influence neighboring countries in the regional arena. Of course, using this resource for this purpose requires strong and intelligent diplomacy. For this reason, Afghanistan needs to be able to properly manage its waters and constructive diplomacy with neighboring countries, and use this resource for peace, construction, reconstruction, and development in Afghanistan and the expansion of beneficial and friendly relations with the

countries of the region (Arya, 2017). In addition, the new Silk Road, which has been undertaken in recent years, is another opportunity that can be effective in the economic and political fields and for the development of Afghanistan in general. This road, which is the heart of Afghanistan's geography, connects the countries of the region by land, on the other hand, connects the Far East and Central Asia to Western Asia and finally to Europe. Therefore, this road will facilitate the transportation and transit process of commercial goods in the region through Afghanistan and provide economic benefits to Afghanistan, on the other hand, it will accelerate the export of Afghan goods to regional and world markets.

1.2. Contemporary Concepts of Migration and Migration Movements

Migration; can be defined as the geographical displacement of people for social, economic, political, or natural reasons. This displacement may be in the form of crossing an international border or within the same state. Regardless of the type of migration (voluntary/forced, temporary/permanent, internal/external, individual/mass, etc.), all kinds of population movements (refugees, asylum seekers, internally displaced people, exiles, economic migrants, etc.) are included in the definition of migration. (Adıgüzel, 2016). Migration; is the temporary or permanent movement of people from one settlement to another. The person who carries out the migration event is defined as an immigrant (refugee). There are reasons why individuals migrate from one place to another. Migration takes place due to the improvement of the economic situation, adverse living conditions, better education opportunities, war, and natural disasters (Yüksel, 2014). It is the movement from one settlement to another with a political border, as an

individual, group, or mass (Seyyar and Genç, 2010). Migration is the placement of individuals, groups, or nations in a new physical and cultural environment due to natural, economic, political, and similar imperatives. Migration; is the geographical displacement of individuals in order to move their lives from one settlement to another or to enter and settle in a new social and cultural environment (Kolukirik, 2006). Fundamental concepts of migration are often confused with each other in political and social debates. However, it is very important to use the concepts correctly for correct migration management. The perspective has listed the basic concepts of migration in the form of a "Dictionary of Migration" below. Immigrant; It covers people and family members who migrate to another country or region in order to improve their financial and social conditions and to increase their or their family's future expectations. Basically, it can be defined as people who leave their country for reasons such as education and work, not because of a justified fear of persecution (Vardar, 2015). Refugee: Those who have been persecuted or feared to be seen because of their religious belief, sect, ethnic origin, political opinion, sexual orientation, or membership of a social group, and therefore have to leave their place of residence or cannot return to this place; These reasons are recognized by the country of asylum (Anonymous, 2020). Asylum is a legal and political right granted by some countries to applicants according to predetermined conditions. The person whose asylum application is accepted gains international protection status and cannot be forced to return to the country from which they came against their own will (Anonymous, 2020). Asylum seeker: A person who seeks security in a country other than his/her own country

due to persecution or serious harm, and awaits a decision on the application for refugee status, according to relevant international and national regulations (Anonymous, 2020). Temporary protection: emergency measures taken in situations where there are obstacles to the implementation of asylum procedures. This includes the protection system provided in Turkey to people who have entered Turkey collectively and whose asylum application will not be considered for international protection (Anonymous, 2020). Forced migration is the situation of forced migration due to conditions that threaten the life or well-being of a person due to natural or man-made reasons (Anonymous, 2020). Economic immigrants are people who prefer to immigrate from their country of residence to another country for economic reasons. Border workers, migrant workers, and seasonal workers are migrants with economic migrant status (Anonymous, 2020). Integration is the process of immigrants' social, individual or social adaptation to the host society. Integration is a frequently discussed concept compared to the concepts of harmony and assimilation, and it is discussed in cultural, economic, and social fields (Anonymous, 2020).

2. AFGHANISTAN AND THE MIGRATION CRISIS

Every year, large numbers of Afghans leave the country in hopes of a better life and work due to poverty, unemployment, and violence. Throughout the history of Afghan immigration, Pakistan and Iran have been the main destinations for the country's immigrants due to their cultural and linguistic proximity. Today, Pakistan and Iran receive 80 percent of all immigrants. The first group of immigrants from Afghanistan went to Pakistan and Iran in the 1970s. The drought, famine, and worsening

economic situation throughout the country in the 70s caused thousands of Afghans to migrate to Middle Eastern countries, especially Iran and Pakistan. One of the events affecting the contemporary history of Afghanistan and causing a great wave of immigration is the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan. With the occupation of Afghanistan by the Soviet Union in 1979, the Cold War turned into a hot conflict. As a result of the destruction and human rights violations caused by the occupation, a great migration wave started for the first time in the history of the country. 1979-1989, more than five million citizens of Afghanistan immigrated to Pakistan, Iran, Turkey, and European countries (Dashti, 2021). In recent years, the US economic sanctions against Iran and the devaluation of the Iranian currency have led to a new wave of Afghan immigration from Iran to Turkey. Many Afghans living in Iran were forced to leave Iran due to the deterioration of the economic situation and the pressure of the Iranian government on the families of Afghan immigrants. A large number of Afghan immigrants entered Turkey through dangerous routes in the hope of reaching European countries. Having failed to find success against the Taliban in Afghanistan for nearly 20 years, the United States signed a peace agreement with the Taliban in Doha in early 2020 to end the longest war in its history on February 29, 2020. By signing the treaty, America ended its military presence in Afghanistan. After the announcement of the United States' complete withdrawal from Afghanistan on July 22, the Taliban soon took over the entire country one after another. When the Taliban arrived at the gates of Kabul on August 15, former President Ashraf Ghani fled the country and the Taliban took over the country for the second time. With the Taliban ruling the country, thousands of

people tried to leave the country to reach the Kabul airport, and as a result of the evacuation process of the United States and other countries, thousands of Afghans working with foreign countries or foreign organizations were evacuated by the United States and other European countries (Dashti, 2021). In addition, the coming to power of the Taliban caused an economic crisis in Afghanistan, and especially drought and famine caused the current economic crisis to deepen. The complete cessation of foreign aid after the Taliban came to power in Afghanistan, which was facing an economic crisis, led to a serious crisis of poverty in the country. On the other hand, the blocking of the assets of the Washington government's Central Bank of Afghanistan deepened the economic problems in the country. The cessation of foreign aid to Afghanistan, which is completely dependent on foreign aid, had a negative impact on the country's economy in this period. A country is considered dependent on foreign aid if more than 10% of its gross domestic product is provided by foreign aid. According to the World Bank, about 40% of Afghanistan's GDP was provided by international aid. This shows how fragile the economic situation of the country is. On the other hand, with the fall of the previous government, many women who support their families and work in government offices are now completely unemployed because the Taliban did not allow other women to attend, except female employees of the Ministry of Public Health. This situation has caused many families to be unable to meet their daily needs. Donor countries have stated that they do not want to help a regime that bans girls from education and supports the return of "sharia punishments"(Dashti, 2021).

2.1. Immigration from Afghanistan to Turkey

Turkey is the third country hosting the most Afghan immigrants after Iran and Pakistan. The history of Afghans' migration to Turkey dates back to the Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan. Approximately 4163 Afghans who migrated from Afghanistan to Pakistan during the occupation immigrated to Turkey legally in 1982. The people in question continue their lives by gaining Turkish citizenship in Turkey (Şimşek, 2021). In recent years, Turkey has become the country of choice for Afghan immigrants due to its geographical location, developing economy, and sharing its borders with Europe. With the beginning of the withdrawal process of the US and NATO forces from Afghanistan in 2014, due to the increasing violence and unemployment in the country, Afghan immigrants turned to Turkey and Europe, and also many Afghan immigrants living in Iran due to the economic sanctions imposed by the USA on Iran in the same years immigrated to Turkey. Most of the Afghans who migrated to Turkey managed to reach the European Union countries in 2015 as a result of the open-door policy of the European Union (Hamsici, 2021). Most of those who cross into Iran aim to reach European and western countries. However, measures have also been increased in Turkey, which currently hosts close to 4 million Syrian refugees and is a stopping point for many migrants trying to reach Europe. These border measures were stepped up as the Taliban began to advance in Afghanistan and took over Kabul. Turkish authorities say that there are 182,000 registered Afghan immigrants and an estimated 120,000 unregistered Afghan immigrants in Turkey (DW, 2021).

3. METHOD OF THE RESEARCH

The method of the research consists of the selection of the sample, the data collection method, and the data evaluation methods. The participants of the research is Afghan immigrants living in Istanbul, Konya, Uşak, and Sakarya. The "survey" method was chosen as the data collection method. Questionnaires were prepared appropriately and applied in the form of face-to-face interviews. The data obtained through the questionnaire were evaluated by preparing tables consisting of frequency and percentage distributions. It was observed that the respondents were generally reluctant to fill out the questionnaires due to some concerns, and this problem was overcome by expressing the objectives of the questionnaire in detail and clearly in Turkish and Persian. The surveys were applied across the provinces from July-December 2021. Research data were collected from 384 Afghan immigrants living in the above provinces of Turkey. The survey consists of three parts. While the first part includes the personal information of the participants such as age, gender, occupation, and education level, the second part includes questions about the reasons for the participants come to Turkey. The third part of the questionnaire is about the problems experienced by the participants. Although the number of Afghan immigrants was high during the survey, not enough answers were received. The most obvious reason for this is the feeling of insecurity. These people, who fled Afghanistan, and became immigrants, refugees, or asylum seekers, refused to participate in the survey for fear of being exposed to the survey or being used against them in the future.

4. FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH
4.1. Socio-Economic Characteristics of Afghan Immigrants

In this part of the study, the aim of determining the socio-demographic characteristics of Afghan immigrants is to have information about the general profiles of Afghan immigrants and to reveal which socio-demographic characteristics, the reasons for their migration, and the problems they experience. The first variable examined was the age of the participants. A person's migration experience is an important factor as well as his/her working life. Some of them leave home and migrate in order to gain economic freedom, learn a new culture, gain non-agricultural work experience, take their own responsibility, make their own decisions in this process. In addition, for some needs such as being a parent and

for them to have developmental criteria and for a better life, they need to participate in employment with a permanent and full-time job. When they cannot find this opportunity in their own country, they decide to migrate to other countries. According to the results of this research, 71.6% of Afghan immigrants in Turkey are between the ages of 21-30. This is followed by the 31-40 age group with 16.4%, the age group 20 and less than 20 years with 10.2%, and the age group 41 and above with 1.8% (Table 1). The results of the research show that Afghan immigrants who immigrated to Turkey are “adult and young individuals”. The mean age of immigrants was calculated as 27.07 (SD =5.627). In this context, the results of the study and similar studies show that Afghan immigrants are mostly adults.

Table 1. Age range of immigrants

Demographic Variables	N	%
Age		
21 - 30	275	71.6
31 - 40	63	16.4
≤ 20	39	10.2
≥ 41	7	1.8
Total	384	100.0
The average age = 27.07		SS = 5.627

Another important variable in migration and working life is gender. The majority (95.1%) of Afghan immigrants participating in the survey are men and 4.9% are women (Table 2). Similarly, Özgün (2021) conducted a research on the Afghan immigrant profile and stated that the gender of Afghan immigrants is 49% female and 51% male, with 128 participants. Akkaş and Aksakal (2021) stated the gender of Afghan immigrants as 63% female and 37% male in their research. In many studies examining irregular Afghan immigrants within the scope of UNHCR regulations, such as the Afghan Migration Survey and the

Afghan Refugee Crisis, the proportion of men who migrated was found to be higher than women. The reason why the ratio of men is higher in this study is that Afghan immigrants pay attention to their agricultural background and this study focused on immigrants who have worked or are working in the agricultural sector in Turkey. Since working in the agricultural sector is heavier and more difficult than in other sectors, men generally work and women (in Afghanistan) take care of housework and children. However, women's role is better in animal husbandry because women living in villages have almost all

livestock experience. The reason for the low number of elderly and women among the Afghan immigrants related to migration is that families, women, children, and the elderly cannot withstand the difficulties of the

migration route (walking for days, crossing mountains and slopes). Also, families and the elderly are compelled to join the war by neither the Taliban nor the government.

Table 2. Gender of immigrants

Demographic Variables	N	%
Gender		
Male	365	95.1
Female	19	4.9
Total	384	100.0

Other variables that show the socio-economic characteristics of immigrants are their marital status, family size, and the number of people who can work or work in the family. When these variables are evaluated alone or together with some other variables in studies, they provide enlightening information about the socio-cultural status of the participants. According to the results of the research, 72.4% of the immigrants are single, 27.1% are married and 0.5% are divorced. The majority of the

immigrants' families (43.2%) are 7-10 people, (40.4%) 4-6 people, (9.4%) 11-13 people, (3.6%) 14 people and above. (3.4%) consists of 3 people and less than 3 individuals. In addition, the average household size of the immigrants is 7.07 and the standard deviation is 3.014 (Table 3). The number of working people in the families of Afghan immigrants who came to Turkey is mostly 2 or fewer (72.1%), 3-4 people (24.5%), and 5 or more (3.4%) people.

Table 3. Marital status of immigrants, family size, and number of working people in the family

Demographic Variables	N	%
Marital Status		
Single	278	72,4
Married	104	27,1
Divorced	2	0,5
Total	384	100,0
Family size		
7 – 10	166	43,2
4 – 6	155	40,4
11 – 13	36	9,4
14 ≤	14	3,6
≤ 3	13	3,4
Total	384	100,0
\bar{x} = 7,07	SS = 3,014	
Number of persons working in the family		
≤ 2	277	72,1
3 – 4	94	24,5
5 ≤	13	3,4
Total	384	100,0

Other variables that show the socio-economic characteristics of the immigrants are their educational status, the jobs they were engaged in before coming to Turkey, and what they were engaged in Turkey. According to the results of the research, 35.7% of the Afghan immigrants who came to Turkey are high school graduates in terms of education level, 26.6% are undergraduate graduates, 20.1% are a secondary school, and 13.5% are illiterate, 3.4% of them are primary school graduates and 0.8% of them are master's graduates (Table 4). Akkaş and Aksakal (2021) made a sociological analysis of attitudes and perceptions toward Afghan immigrants, and they found that the education level of Afghan

immigrants were 3.5% illiterate, 23% primary school, 24.5% high school, and 49% are undergraduate graduates. This study shows that immigrants earned their living by working in different sectors in Afghanistan, as 20.1% were unemployed, 19.5% were students, 16.7% were in the agricultural sector, 12.5% established their own profession, 12.2% were workers, 12% were in private institutions, 4.4% were civil servants, 2.1% were housewives, and 0.5% were working in restaurants (Table 4). In another similar study, more than half of the Afghan immigrants participating in the research stated that 32% worked in the education sector and 21% in the agriculture sector before emigrating (Özgün, 2021).

Table 4. Educational status and occupations before migration

Demographic Variables	N	%
Education Status		
Illiterate	52	13.5
Primary education	13	3.4
Middle school	77	20.1
High school graduate	137	35.7
Bachelor's degree	102	26.6
Master	3	.8
Total	384	100.0
Jobs he was busy with before he immigrated		
Unemployed	77	20.1
Student	75	19.5
Agriculture sector	64	16.7
Own profession	48	12.5
Workmanship	47	12.2
Private institutions	46	12.0
Civil servant	17	4.4
Housewife	8	2.1
Restaurant	2	.5
Total	384	100.0

Due to Afghanistan's civil war, deteriorating economic situation, increasing unemployment rate, and many other reasons, the Afghan nation first migrated to neighboring countries of Afghanistan, then to Turkey and European countries to move themselves

to a safe place and to support their families economically. When we examine the occupations, we see that those who work in factories take the largest share (31.8%) (Table 5). In other similar studies, it is observed that the vast majority of Afghan immigrants

work informally in Turkey. In the report of the Mixed Migration Center, most Afghan immigrants in Turkey stated that they work daily jobs in the construction industry, herding field, factories, and textile workshops. It also stated that the beneficiaries of international protection mainly work in sectors such as agriculture and sheep raising that do not require a work permit. In the report titled "Ghosts of Istanbul: Afghans on the

Edge of Precariousness" prepared by the Migration Research Association, Afghan immigrants who came to Turkey as early as the 1990s had bakeries, restaurants, and small shops in Istanbul, but this group of immigrants only covers 10% to 20% of it. However, it is stated that the Afghan immigrants who came later mostly worked in daily jobs that require intense physical labor (Hamsici, 2021).

Table 5. Jobs that immigrants are occupied in Turkey

Demographic Variables	N	%
In field and irrigation	55	14.3
Farming	41	10.7
Shepherding	18	4.7
Orchard	3	.8
Factory	122	31.8
Daily worker	45	11.7
Student	31	8.1
Unemployed	31	8.1
Restaurant	25	6.5
Own job (occupation)	10	2.6
Housewife	3	.8
Total	384	100.0

4.2. Reasons for Afghan Immigrants to Migrate and Choose Turkey

One of the main reasons for Afghan migration has been migration due to economic and unemployment reasons. However, due to conflicts, the rate of migration has increased and the results have differed (Geyik, 2018). In addition to all these negativities that justify immigration in Afghanistan, immigration to cities with kinship ties and outside borders also has an important place. Among the people in the migrated region; a close bond is established depending on the common origin, kinship, and friendship relations, and later immigrants benefit from the different experiences of those who migrated before them, and this happens in a cyclical manner. People in Afghanistan are forced to migrate voluntarily or from places of exile for

economic reasons and to protect their life safety. Although exile migrations in Afghanistan are generally due to socio-economic reasons, war appears as another reason. In addition, these migrations are made by force or threat, and threats are usually carried out by armed people. Along with these, the proliferation of evils in the world forced people to leave their lands at the cost of their lives in order to find peace. Some flee in order to find a job in a rich country and take care of their family in their hometown, while others take the road to save their lives by taking their entire family with them. People who migrate to escape war and torture begin to experience psychological problems over time. In order to overcome these, it sometimes enters the process of getting used to this situation, either compulsory or willingly (Obayd and Karataş, 2021).

As the Table 6 shows, the most important reasons that push the immigrants participating in the research to migrate are the economic problems and increasing unemployment rate in Afghanistan 46.1%, the fear of terrorism and the increase in the civil war in the country 44.3%, and the increase in the civil war in the country 9%. 0.6 of them stated that they migrate voluntarily and for educational purposes. When we asked the immigrants why they did not go to another country, and the answers we received, 46.9% stated that they came to Turkey to find more job opportunities, to provide a prosperous life and a good education for their children in the future. 46.1% of them came to Turkey on the recommendation of their friends or friends or their relatives have lived in Turkey before, 4.2% find Turkish culture close to Afghan culture, and 2.9% come to Turkey to go to European countries. On the other hand, when asked about their satisfaction level of immigrants

coming to Turkey, 60.2% said they were satisfied, 22.4% were very satisfied, 8.3% were undecided, 6.5% were not satisfied, and 2.6% said they were satisfied. As Table 6 shows, most immigrants are satisfied with immigrating to Turkey and the reasons for this satisfaction are having a regular job in Turkey, living with their family in Turkey, being able to go to school with their children, and most importantly, being able to go to work safely in the mornings and in the evenings their ability to return home to their family. Looking at the results of the research, it was stated that a small part of the immigrants was not satisfied with emigrating to Turkey, and the reasons for this were that their families were devastated in Afghanistan, and they could not find the right and regular job in Turkey, basic needs became expensive, and the salary they received working here was not enough for them and their families.

Table 6. Reasons for Afghan immigrants to migrate and choose Turkey

Migration status of Afghan immigrants to Turkey	N	%
Reasons to migrate		
Economic problems and increasing unemployment rate in Afghanistan	177	46.1
Fear of terrorism and escalation of civil war in the country	170	44.3
Migrating themselves voluntarily or for educational purposes	37	9.6
Total	384	100.0
Reasons to choose Turkey		
Finding more job opportunities in Turkey. providing a prosperous life and a good education for their children in the future	180	46.9
Having lived in Turkey before. on the advice of friends and friends or relatives	177	46.1
Finding Turkish culture close to Afghan culture	16	4.2
Traveling from Turkey to European countries	11	2.9
Total	384	100.0
Satisfaction with immigration		
I am very pleased	86	22.4
I am satisfied	231	60.2
I'm undecided	32	8.3
I am not satisfied	25	6.5
I am not happy at all	10	2.6
Total	384	100.0

4.3. Problems Faced By Afghan Immigrants

While trying to adapt to their new country, immigrants may experience many problems related to the dynamics within the family. Especially newly arrived immigrants, they face problems such as language and cultural differences, inability to afford a house to rent, employment, health, and education. In order to cope with these problems, Afghan immigrants work in hard jobs with low wages and these problems are listed below. In terms of accommodation: Afghan immigrants living in Turkey and those who participated in the research stated that they faced a series of problems such as finding a place to stay, paying rent, and struggling with the cold and dampness in the winter months. Afghan immigrants who have come before earning their living and support the new arrivals in this context. In the future where Afghan immigrants live, Afghan immigrants who lived there before help with shelter, nutrition, and official work of refugees/asylum seekers. Migrants try to live in that province and meet some of their basic needs by using the migrant relations network among themselves through some associations or Facebook or WhatsApp groups at the first stage they arrive and afterward. In terms of employment and economy: All Afghan immigrants surveyed have worked or continue to work in the informal sector in harsh conditions, and Afghan immigrants work long hours, often for lower wages than other workers. When we look at the results of other studies, the problems encountered in the field of employment are similar to the problems experienced by other refugees and asylum seekers living in Turkey. In terms of health and health services: Afghan immigrants living in Turkey state that they usually go to state

hospitals when they are sick. In this context, when Afghan immigrants participating in the research were asked whether they had problems in health institutions, the most common problems were language difficulties, high drug and treatment fees because they did not have health insurance, and sometimes they could not pay for the medicine and took half of the medicines, and they encountered such problems. In terms of education: One of the most fundamental problems faced by individuals in accessing educational opportunities in their country of origin is that immigrants do not have an identity. For this reason, Afghan immigrants have problems accessing education services and this makes language learning difficult for immigrants.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the historical process, migration has significantly affected international relations and the world order and continues to affect it. Civil wars, conflicts, bloody struggles, political pressures, education, natural disasters, climate changes, famine, hunger, and epidemics, especially economic problems, have become one of the main problem areas of the world and humanity as millions of people have to leave their lands. The largest and most massive migration in the history of Afghanistan started with the invasion of Afghanistan by the Soviet Union. During the Soviet occupation between 1979-1989, more than 5 million Afghans were displaced and immigrated to neighboring countries. The second largest mass migration is the turmoil and instability created by the Civil War in Afghanistan. In this study, we tried to understand the socio-economic characteristics of Afghan immigrants based on their experiences in the migration process and

examine the reasons for their migration. We evaluated our findings and results in terms of the socio-economy of the immigrants and then the reasons for their arrival in Turkey. Long-term conflicts and drought and famine caused by climate change, which have created an uncertain economic and political situation in Afghanistan recently, have forced about 7 million Afghans to leave their homeland and migrate to other countries in order to find a better life. In addition, Afghanistan has been one of the countries that produce the most migration in the world due to the internal conflicts it has experienced for more than forty years. Currently, the largest group of Afghan immigrants living in Pakistan and Iran. Afghan immigrants turned to Turkey in order to reach Europe in 2014 with the deterioration of security in the country. Currently, Afghans constitute the second largest immigrant group in Turkey after Syrians. Following the complete withdrawal of US and NATO forces from Afghanistan on July 22 and the Taliban takeover of Afghanistan on August 15, another mass exodus took place in Afghanistan. The fall of the Kabul government and the cessation of foreign aid have deepened the economic crisis in Afghanistan and increased poverty. These developments once again initiated the flow of external migration in the country. Especially in these years, qualified human migration, which can contribute to the development of the country, has had irreversible results in the country. In order to prevent the Afghan migration crisis that has been going on for years, first of all, political and economic stability must be ensured. In order to ensure economic and political stability in the country, it is necessary to establish an inclusive and unifying government that includes all ethnic groups. In terms of economy, since the country's economy is predominantly

based on agriculture, agricultural policies and programs should be developed and farmers should be supported. In addition, development projects that will provide employment and encourage equal growth should be implemented in all regions of the country, including rural areas. Otherwise, the influx of Afghan immigrants, which affects almost the whole world, will continue indefinitely.

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